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VIRTUAL REALITY: THE IMAGINATION OF ORIGINALITY

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ABSTRACT

Virtual Reality (VR), also called as Virtual Environments (VE) has drawn much attention in the last few decades. The Virtual Reality make use of a huge number of technologies in order to produce a Imaginary world so that a user can interact with the virtual objects in the so produced Virtual Worlds. With the assistance of some specially developed gadgets such as Head Mounted Display, Electronic Gloves and Mechanical armatures which fit the human organs that we can immerse the human into this Virtual world. This simulation technique is combined along with the motion of the humans to produce the output that what human expect for. In this paper an overview of virtual reality is presented along with the types, architecture of VR system, followed by applications of this technology in science, work, and entertainment areas. Finally, the future of VR is considered[2].

Key words: VR, VE, Head Mounted Display, Electronic Gloves and Mechanical armatures

I. INTRODUCTION

“Virtual Reality is one of the way for the humans to visualize, manipulate and interact with computers and extremely the complex data”.

Here the word ‘visualization’ refers to the computer-generated outputs such as the computer graphics, simulations, and other factors such as the CAD models, etc.,. Here the outputs may be the animations that can be controlled easily by the scripts. Here the human can directly interact and manipulate with these kind of animations.[4]

The most difficult thing in the Virtual Reality is to produce the interaction between the Virtual world and the human. The type of Virtual Reality in which the human is immersed into the Virtual world is called as the immersive Virtual Reality. In such types of Virtual Reality, the human is completely isolated from outside world and is placed in an entirely computer generated world.

The applications that are being developed for Virtual Reality have a wide range utilities. Among them, the real time applications occupy the most prominent place.[6]

II. TYPES OF VIRTUAL REALITY SYSTEM

The different kinds of Virtual Reality systems are:

(a) Immersive Systems

The highest priority is being given to immersive systems. As already mentioned, the immersive systems rules out the entire real world and places the humans in a completely computer-generated animation world.

(b) Window on World (WoW)

It is the normal Virtual world that has been developed on the desktop. The most common form of the WoW, are computer games that uses the 3-d simulation of the real world. Here, the user has to peep into the Virtual world using the monitor placed on his/her desktop.

(c) Video Mapping

This is the technique that is used to map the motion of a human, using a special electronic device such as camera. Here, the input to the computer is the motion of the human and the output is a 2-d graphical image of a human showing the human.

(d) Tele presence

This is another technique in Virtual Reality where we use some remote sensors that is placed somewhere in the Virtual world ,that maps the human actions and associates them with the actions that has to be done by the objects in the Virtual world. Such type of Virtual Reality is being used by the fire-fighters in some critical conditions. Special Robots fixed with this type of sensors, help them.

(e) Mixed Reality

This is a technique combining the Virtual Reality systems with the telepresence. Here the inputs to both the telepresence and Virtual Reality systems are fed into them as the inputs. The fighters see the maps that are generated by the computers and associate them with the data available in them. The surgeons correlate these images taken by the CT scans taken by the computers.[1]

III. TECHNOLOGIES IN VR :

After a deep study of this emerging technology, the VR is classified into three kinds. They are:

1. Virtual Reality using Hardware

There is a number of hardware that are developed for the usage by Virtual Reality. Among them some are:

1.1 Head Mounted Display

The Head mounted display consists mainly of two miniature display screens that produce the stereoscopic images and an optical positioned tracking system that tracks the orientations of the human head in the Virtual world and that produces impulse to the image-generating computer. The image-generating computer produces the view corresponding to the orientation of the user's head in the Virtual world. This is the basic device that is used in the IVR. As a result the user can view in the direction that he/she wants and can walk through the Imaginary world.

1.2 Boom and Cave

To overcome the tactlessness with, the HMD, the Boom and Cave are used. These are also extensively used for the IVR.[8]

Screens and stereoscopic image generating apparatus are fixed in one box, which is attached to a multi-linked arm. The user peeps into the Virtual world through the holes, and controls the motions with the arms.

Fig. 1

A cave consists of a cube-shaped room. The stereo-scopical images are projected onto the walls and the floor of the hall with the help of projectors. Several users may sit together on the Virtual world at a time.

Fig. 2

Virtual Reality using softwares

The most commonly used tools for developing 3-d worlds are VRML v1.0, VRML97, VRML , 3d Studio max, Rhino3d, Amapi3d, ALICE99, BLENDER and other such softwares. The VRMLv1.0 is a child

language that is developed from the XML family. There is no much differences between the later versions of VRML. The programming paradigms are entirely different in VRMLv1.0 to VRMLv2.0. There are many companies that are dedicated to develop the tools for creating the virtual worlds, such as Parallel Graphics Co., Trapezium Co., etc.. [3]

IV. ARCHITECTURE OF VR SYSTEM

Fig. 3

The Components of VR System :

- (a) Input Processor,
- (b) Simulation Processor,
- (c) Rendering Processor and
- (d) World Database

(a) Input Processor

-Controls the devices that are used to input, information to the computer. The objective is to get the coordinate data to the rest of the system with a minimal lag time.

-Keyboard, mouse, 3-D position tracker, voice recognition system, etc.[7]

(b) Simulation Processor

-is theCore of a VR system.

-It Takes the user inputs along with any other tasks programmed into the world and determine the actions that would take place in the virtual world.

(c) Rendering Processor

-It Creates the sensations that are output to the user.

-It Separates the rendering processes,and are used for visuals, auditory, haptics and other sensory-systems. [9]

V. APPLICATIONS

The Real Time Applications of Virtual Reality:

The applications being developed for the Virtual Reality run over a wide spectrum from 3-d games to architectural planning of buildings and so on. The applications may be scientific or technical that cannot be viewed in the actual life. The flexibility of the Virtual Reality, makes it use in the scientific applications such as architectural planning, rocket launching, war strategies, cockpit simulation, robotics and other medical related applications.[12]

SIMNET is the first war-related Virtual Reality application that is developed. This project is standardized, being pushed by the USA Defense Department in order to enable the diverse simulators to be interconnected into vast network. The soldiers can be trained to the war by developing the Virtual world that looks exactly like the war field. This helps them in knowing, how to deal in war fields. Distributed Interactive System (DIS) protocol has been developed by Orlando Institute of Training and Simulation, which is the future of Virtual Reality in the war strategies.

Virtual Reality is now used to train physicians in order to carry out intricate surgical procedures like laparoscopies, endoscopies and other minimally invasive surgeries. Nanosurgery is another medical application, where the doctors are located at a distinct place guided the robots. They guide the robots with the help of the multi-linked arms.

Virtual Reality helps in designing the virtual models of certain objects. By building the virtual models, we can see how that model works, what the defects may be, and how we can overcome the defects. These all cannot be seen by developing the model as it also includes a lot of cost and labour. This concept of Virtual Reality is being used in the designing of conceptual cars. Virtual reality provides the tool for evaluating such designs in full scale without costly physical prototypes.[10]

VII. FUTURE OF VR

Yesterday, Virtual Reality was a science fiction fantasy. Today, it is a research topic in laboratories and amusement parks. Tomorrow, it will certainly replace our televisions and computers. There are already many organizations deemed towards the development of the Virtual Reality. Many researches are being done in order to find more and more applications of Virtual Reality. In the forthcoming days the web-sites developed using Virtual Reality will replace the entire present web industries. Even a virtual Jurassic Park may be developed, in a short span of days. Let us hope for a bright future of this emerging technologies.[11]

VIII. CONCLUSION:

The technology is developing rapidly and shows a considerable potential. The ability of Virtual Reality in order to produce realistic worlds of data, objects and environments, with which the users can interact with a realistic and an spontaneous manner, opens up a vast wealth of possibilities for the work-related applications. The concept of Virtual Reality provides an innovative mixture of entertainment, education and State of Art. Virtual reality will transport guests to different kind of worlds. From water-beds to gyroscopes and hydraulic units, a variety of platforms will provide us a new kind of travel; into the Cyberspace; into virtual worlds where one can be able to swim with the dolphins and experience intense sensory stimulations.[5] As the movement of people is becoming more and more costly with the time, the scope of Virtual Reality is growing more. Working in many fields like the medicine, rocket launching, massive constructions, it is very much important to be more precise and accurate and here Virtual Reality gives a solution by providing a platform which makes it possible by using these applications of Virtual Reality.

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